

INTEGRATED WATERSHED MANAGEMENT Approaches to Alleviating Poverty in the Bicol Region, Philippines *Learning from Past Experience*

Report from a regional
learning workshop

IIRR

INTERNATIONAL INSTITUTE OF RURAL RECONSTRUCTION

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There should be a demand-driven, community-based approach to watershed management involving two parallel components. Firstly, one where the demands are determined by national priorities and concerns. Secondly, one in which there is direct conservation, planning, management and sustainable utilization (for multiple purposes) of their local watershed resources. The aim of both is to provide the optimum social, cultural, economic and environmental benefits to the greatest number of people, particularly those living in, adjacent to, or downstream of individual watershed areas while maintaining the biological and cultural heritage of the Philippines.

- Philippines Strategy for Improved Watershed Resources Management,
DEPARTMENT OF ENVIRONMENT AND NATURAL RESOURCES (DENR), 1998

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Acronyms

APP	Annual Program Plan
BRBDP	Bicol River Basin Development Program
BUCAF	Bicol University College of Agriculture and Forestry
CBO	community-based organization
CBRM	community-based resource management program
CBRPP	community-based resource protection program
CENRO	City Environment and Natural Resources Office
CN-LRM	Camarines Norte-Local Resource Management Office
CO	community organization
CSSAC	Camarines Sur State Agricultural College
DA	Department of Agriculture
DAR	Department of Agrarian Reform
DBM	Department of Budget and Management
DENR	Department of Environment and Natural Resources
DENR-PAO	Department of Environment and Natural Resources - Protected Areas Office
DIP	detailed implementation plan
DO	dissolved oxygen
DOF	Department of Finance
DOH	Department of Health
DOST	Department of Science and Technology
DOT	Department of Tourism
DPWH	Department of Public Works and Highways
DTI	Department of Trade and Industry
ENRO	Environment and Natural Resources Office
EMC	Environment Management Council
EWAMP	ecological waste management program
FARMC	Fisheries and Aquatic Resource Management Council
FIDA	Fiber Industries Development Authority
FGD	focused group discussion
GEF-MSP	Global Environment Facility - Medium-sized projects
GO	government organization
GOP	Government of the Philippines
ICLARM	World Fish Center
IIRR	International Institute of Rural Reconstruction
IWM	integrated watershed management
LCE	local chief executive
LDC	local development council
LGC	Local Government Code
LGU	local government unit
LIBON-CBRMP	Libon Resources Management Project - Community Based Resource Management Project
LIKAS	Lingap para sa Kalusugan ng Sambayanan
LRMP	Local Resource Management Project
LWUA	Local Water Utilities Administration
MIG	Mt. Isarog Guardians
MIICD	Mt. Isarog Integrated Conservation and Development Project

MMAPP	Mt. Masaraga Agroforestry Pilot Project
MNWD	Metro Naga Water District
MOA	memorandum of agreement
MOU	memorandum of understanding
M & E	monitoring and evaluation
NCPC	Naga City People's Council
NEDA	National Economic Development Authority
NGA	national government agency
NGO	non-government organization
NIPAP	National Integrated Protected Areas Program
NIPAS	National Integrated Protected Areas System
NRM	natural resource management
PAMB	Protected Area Management Board
PAWD	Philippine Association of Water Districts
PDS	provincial development strategies
PPCC	Provincial Policy Coordinating Council
PPDO	Provincial Planning and Development Office
PO	people's organization
PRA	participatory rural appraisal
PVO	private voluntary organization
RDC	Regional Development Council
RPCC	Regional Policy Coordinating Council
RRDP	Rainfed Resources Development Program
TRA	threat reduction analysis
SALT	sloping agricultural land technology
SALUD san Diwata	Sahod Agos Lahat Umaasa sa Daloy ng Diwata (a community-based network)
SAT	special action team
SEC	Securities and Exchange Commission
SHG	self help group
SMI-MFER	San Miguel Island - Marine Fishery Reserve
SMMBSR	Samahang Maliliit na Mangingisda ng Bonot - Sta. Rosa
SUMMIT	Sustainable Management of Mt. Isarog's Territories
SWIP	small water impounding project
TSS	total suspended solids
UNEP	United Nations Environment Program
USAID	United States Agency for International Development
VCA	village community assembly
WB	World Bank

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First, are the individuals who participated in the IWM workshop held in May 2003 – various stakeholders from the Bicol region and the organizations they represent. Each of them generously shared their practical experiences, including what have worked and what have not worked in natural resource management, in an effort to find environmentally viable approaches to promote development in the region's most impoverished rural areas. The invaluable contributions of these individuals and organizations to new knowledge and lessons in natural resource management have been synthesized in this publication and are being made available for practitioners, educators, policy makers and others who may wish to further study and undertake more holistic and integrated approaches to addressing rural poverty while keeping the integrity of the environment.

From the conceptualization and planning to the implementation of this learning workshop, many agencies of the national government and leading academic institutions, local city and municipal governments, and non-government organizations contributed invaluable ideas and resources. From the academe these include, the Bicol University, and the Camarines Sur State Agricultural College (CSSAC). The Naga City government was an active participant in the process. Line agencies of the national government in Region V, such as the Departments of Environment and Natural Resources, Agrarian Reform, Agriculture, and the National Economic Development Authority also provided inputs, based on the lessons of many of their programs and projects. Several NGOs, namely the Haribon Foundation, the Social Action Center, the International Institute of Rural Reconstruction, and LIKAS helped to provide perspectives and concerns of civil society organizations, organizations in close touch with the grassroots.

Representatives from these various organizations reflecting multi-perspectives constituted a project steering committee and a technical working group which strategically guided and supported planning for the workshop. More specifically, they developed the workshop framework, helped to refine the workshop design, identified distinctive program and project experiences in the region worth studying, and reviewed and screened the papers and case studies.

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This initiative is a step forward in the continuing effort to put integrated watershed resources management into action in the Bicol region. The workshop may have been completed but the need to learn and share continues.

Learning Workshop

Sharing is learning, and the sharing of lessons is priceless.
– Workshop participants

Photo credits: <http://www.geology.wisc.edu/~rschott/g100/mayon.html>

Background

Amidst vast tracts of arable agricultural land and rich natural resources, the Bicol region of the Philippines remains the second poorest region in the country (National Census and Statistics Board, CY 2000). Poverty in Bicol is aggravated by unabated degradation of fast depleting natural resources, on which 80 per cent of the population of the region depends for food and income.

Both the government and non-government sectors have attempted to integrate conservation into development approaches in project implementation, to begin to address the problem in a sustainable way. But while some progress has been achieved, it is difficult to assess effectiveness or success, as few comparative lessons on integrated natural resources management have been documented. Project experiences in Bicol, as elsewhere, have not been widely shared across organizations and thus, new projects are implemented each time without the benefit of building on the successes, failures and lessons of the past.

Definitions of integrated watershed management

Integrated watershed management (IWM) is a comprehensive, multi-resource management planning process involving all stakeholders within a watershed who, together as a group, cooperatively work toward identifying the watershed's resource issues and concerns, as well as developing and implementing a watershed plan with solutions that are environmentally, socially, and economically sustainable.

- Alberta watershed, n.d.

IWM can also be described in general terms as "a form of coordinated management of land and water resources within a region, with the objective of preventing land degradation, protecting the quality of freshwater resources, protecting biodiversity and continuing sustainable use within a context which includes genuine community-government partnership and recognition of socio-economic objectives."

- Marino and Simonovic (eds.), 2001

Integrated watershed management is the process of formulating and carrying out a course of action in a watershed to provide goods and services without adversely affecting the soil and water base, taking into account the social, economic and institutional factors operating within and outside the watershed to achieve specific objectives.

- Hufschmitt, 1985

management of natural resources. Farmers and fisherfolk directly affected by natural resources degradation may also benefit in the long run from future development projects that may be influenced by the lessons outlined here.

Workshop objectives

The IWM workshop aimed to provide a platform to:

- ◆ discuss, share and exchange knowledge and experience on field-tested integrated watershed resources management strategies, methods and techniques, including those that have worked or failed, and the reasons for their success or failure;
- ◆ document lessons from these experiences, underscoring how to identify and define problems (the information and processes required), set priorities, formulate strategies, select technologies, implement, monitor and evaluate programs and projects, and sustain their impact;

To address the challenge of bringing together, consolidating, and synthesizing lessons from natural resources management projects in the region for greater sharing and learning, the INTERNATIONAL INSTITUTE OF RURAL RE-CONSTRUCTION (IIRR) initiated a three-day workshop held at the Camarines Sur State Agricultural College in Pili, Camarines Sur in May 2003.

IIRR advocates learning from past experiences as essential to developing effective and sustainable programs to address rural poverty. By documenting these lessons, IIRR and the partners involved in this initiative hope to distill key elements of a holistic program framework for integrated watershed management (IWM).

Envisioned as a learning initiative, the workshop provided a platform for sharing field-tested knowledge, experiences, strategies, and approaches as they have been adopted by natural resource programs and projects in Bicol over the past decade.

This report is a distillation of some of the most important lessons and proven practices in managing natural resources as they have been applied in Bicol. It also offers a guidepost for the design of integrated watershed management programs and projects and may prove useful for other areas and regions of the country.

The publication is intended for the use of local government agencies, rural development planners and practitioners, people's and community-based organizations, non-government organizations, and other stakeholders who support sustainable

- ◆ formulate an operational framework for integrated watershed management and strategies based on best practices and lessons learned; and
- ◆ share the output of the workshop to a broad range of organizations, institutions, and decision-makers in the Bicol region and elsewhere.

Workshop process

Multi-stakeholder processes, particularly consultation meetings and workshop-based technology of participation techniques were the methodologies employed to design and conduct the workshop. The entire learning process used is outlined in Figure 1 (see page 4).

Preparation for the workshop involved the following activities:

- identification of key partners and stakeholders in the Bicol region,
- identification of distinctive program and project experiences, and
- formulation of case study guidelines to distill the important lessons from programs and projects in natural resources management.

The integrated watershed management or IWM approach represents a shift from traditional decision making processes affecting development, where the natural environment and human systems are considered independently of one another. The communities along a watershed are bound by a shared resource, regardless of whether these communities fall along different geographic boundaries or are governed by different political administrative units as municipalities and provinces. Adhering to the principle that the lives of communities located within a watershed are interconnected, all sectors within this resource must work collectively to deal with the sometimes conflicting issue of resource use to relieve poverty and resource conservation and sustainability.

Various line agencies of the national government and leading academic institutions, local city and municipal governments, and non-government organizations in Bicol were partners in this initiative. Specifically, these include, BICOL UNIVERSITY COLLEGE OF AGRICULTURE AND FORESTRY (BUCAF), CAMARINES SUR STATE AGRICULTURAL COLLEGE (CSSAC), NAGA CITY GOVERNMENT, SOCIAL ACTION CENTER (SAC), the DEPARTMENT OF ENVIRONMENT AND NATURAL RESOURCES (DENR), DEPARTMENT OF AGRARIAN REFORM (DAR), DEPARTMENT OF AGRICULTURE (DA), NATIONAL ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT AUTHORITY (NEDA), HARIBON FOUNDATION and LINGAP PARA SA KALUSUGAN NG SAMBAYANAN (LIKAS). Representatives from these organizations constituted a project steering committee and a technical working group which provided strategic support and guidance, including developing the framework and mechanics for the workshop, identifying distinctive program/project experiences in the region, reviewing and screening papers and case studies, and refining the workshop design and process.

During the workshop, case studies were presented and analyzed in three stages. In the first stage, participants reviewed and analyzed cases within each of the three major ecosystems – upland, coastal, and watershed – to distill unique, as well as common lessons. They were grouped according to the major ecosystem clusters; each group was provided with a set of guide questions, the objective of which was to draw out the key learning points from each case experience.

Figure 1 **Learning Process**

In the second stage, the participants analyzed the cases across ecosystems, utilizing the outputs of the first analysis and guided by the additional set of questions, from which they drew common lessons from across all three ecosystems.

On the basis of the first two stages of review and analysis, participants evolved the elements of a framework for integrated watershed management. They identified the key operational phases for the IWM approach, they identified parameters for assessing performance, and they proposed immediate and long-term action plans in support of IWM efforts.

With the aim of communicating and disseminating the lessons and outputs from the workshop, this report has been shared to development audiences within the region. IIRR and the partners hope that the main recommendations outlined in the report can form the basis for specific actions to be undertaken through continued inter-organizational collaboration to advance IWM approaches in the Bicol region.

Learning from Past Experience

Revealing the past gives people a say in their future. It gives the courage to act and the power to dream.

– Waitt Family Foundation, 2003

Ecosystems as basis for collective review, analysis and learning

Following the Earth Summit in 1992, and other landmark actions on the environment that preceded it, a number of natural resources-based programs and projects have been implemented in the Bicol region following an 'ecosystem approach'. The approach highlights the interconnection and interdependence between the

environment and human systems, and the need for civil society organizations, government agencies and rural communities to organize in new and more cooperative ways.

*The **ecosystem perspective** is applicable at all scales, from microscopic to local, watershed to regional and global scale. What happens at one scale determines what happens at other scales. With multiple pressures from population, demographic shifts and resource use, ecological patterns and processes can be altered at any scale.*

– Johnson and Campbell,
1999

***Ecosystem management** or an ecosystem approach refers to ways of relating to and using the ecosystem we are part of, in ways that ensure protection, maintenance and restoration for the benefits of both humans, animals and plants.*

– Hammond, 1993

In Bicol, an ecosystem approach to natural resource management has been applied variedly, depending on the objectives, scale of interest, resources, and practical convenience of the implementing agencies. The proponents had realized that each project was actually embedded within larger ecosystem, such as a watershed.

The upland, lowland, and coastal zones and watersheds are functional units of an ecosystem. To capture the various project experiences, an ecosystem perspective was adopted throughout the learning process as a way to categorize and unify lessons. Based on a review of natural resources programs and projects in the region for possible case study development, three common types of ecosystems emerge: upland, coastal, and watershed.

Profiling regional experiences

The profiling, review and analysis of program and project experiences in natural resources management in the region was based on this ecosystem approach. Thirty program or project experiences were originally identified for case study development. Upland ecosystem-based projects represented 53% of the cases reviewed, coastal and watershed ecosystem-based projects represent 27% and 13% of the cases, respectively, 7% were in the others category. The cases were drawn from the provinces of Albay, Camarines Sur, Sorsogon, Catanduanes, and Camarines Norte. The majority were projects implemented by local government units in the region; the others were projects of government agencies and non-government organizations (NGOs).

Using the guidelines prepared by the steering committee and the technical working group, 16 case studies representing upland, coastal and watershed ecosystems were selected and prepared for further review and analysis. Five of the cases were projects implemented by the government line agencies, another five by local government units. Three case studies each were projects implemented by academic institutions and non-government organizations. All provinces of the region, with the exception of Catanduanes, were represented in the selected cases. However, not all the common ecosystem-type programs and projects were present in projects in each province. The cases were processed at two levels. First, an initial review and screening was conducted by the steering committee and the technical working group. Second, they were presented and analyzed by the workshop participants for important lessons.

Coastal ecosystem

Refers to areas such as estuaries, tidal zones, or near shore and offshore. Each of these areas has its own dynamic characteristics which varies with region, climate, and ocean current flow. For instance, an estuary is a 'hybrid' environment incorporating terrestrial and marine, lake and ocean dynamics. A tidal zone or near shore area consists mainly of mangroves, lagoons, and salt marshes. An offshore area consists of open water or coral reefs and/or islands.

- Chowdhury, et. al., n.d.

Upland ecosystem

Refers to lands of gentle slope (8% and above), with moderate fertility, on which the agricultural system is generally feasible, and the hilly lands, which are predominantly acidic and infertile. Generally, upland ecosystems are characterized by declining productivity, subsistence farming, deforestation and insecure land tenure.

- Garrity and Sajise, 1990

Watershed ecosystem

The concept of watershed and ecosystem are inextricably linked with watershed boundaries, which refers to how living systems interact with their physical environment that is defined by a ridgeline or topographical divide and drained by a river and its tributaries. The uplands communities, lowlands, wetlands, riparian areas, coastal areas, rivers, lakes and streams are the critical features within a watershed ecosystem.

- Alberta watersheds, n.d.

Table 1. Case papers presented at the workshop

COASTAL ECOSYSTEM

Coastal environment program implementation in Prieto Diaz, Sorsogon, Philippines: Insights into coastal resources co-management. Pobleo M. Florence, Rebecca R. Matusalem, Ruby L. Mendones

Initiatives on sustainable Capiz fishery: The case of San Miguel Bay. Ronald Lachica

Managing “badoy” fisheries of Sorsogon Bay: Challenges to effective interface of roles of academe, LGU and local community. Ronnel R. Dioneda Sr., and Victor S. Soliman

Reviving the stock of Sinarapan, “the world’s smallest commercial fish:” Adapting biodiversity conservation and co-community science application. Victor S. Soliman and Antonino B. Mendoza, Jr.

San Miguel Island marine fishery reserve: Lessons on local governance and co-management, Tabaco City. Victor S. Soliman

UPLAND ECOSYSTEM

Community-based resource protection program: Mt. Isarog Natural Park. Crisostomo S. Rivero and Jocelyn A. Nique

Community-based forest resource management project, Tible, Sipocot, Camarines Sur. Vivencio M. Cabanayan and Angelito I. Rutaquio

Mt. Bulusan Volcano Natural Park: Community-based resources management. Aydelfe N. Salvadora

Mt. Masaraga agro-forestry pilot project. Antonio P. Payonga, Jerry S. Bigornia and Jeffrey Sapillar

Reduction of direct threats to biodiversity: An alternative measure of success of conservation initiatives for Mt. Isarog Natural Park. Esteban Paga, Alexander D. Nayve and Roy Layosa

Local resource management project in Arimbay, Legazpi City. Ma. Beatriz B. Barela and Yole Palmiano

WATERSHED ECOSYSTEM

Don Tomas small water impounding project, Sta. Elena, Camarines Sur. Department of Agriculture

Developing partnership for sustainable watershed management in Mt. Isarog: The MNWD experience. Vicente A. Rubio

Community-based resource management project: Abasig-Matagdon watershed development sub-project. Provincial CBRM Team, Camarines Norte

Best practices in Naga City river strategic watershed management program. Oscar P. Orozco

Libon resource management project: Community-based resource management. John V. Dycoco, Leonardo M. Olivares, Salve M. Nidea and Jeffrey R. Sapillar

Important Lessons

You cannot understand a system until you try to change it.
 –Kurt Lewin, as cited by Edgar Schein, 1995

To achieve both poverty reduction and sustainable natural resources management, resource managers must employ the right mix of technical interventions and management strategies. This involves on-site management practices, the appropriate scale of operation, full-time planning, review and personnel, working partnerships, institutional and governance arrangements, and a supportive or enabling policy environment. In analyzing the case studies presented during the workshop, the participants drew out unique — as well as common — lessons from across all three ecosystems.

Lessons within ecosystems

For this assessment, unique lessons refer to features peculiar to particular ecosystem-based programs and projects. The purpose of the analysis is to highlight strategies that have worked or failed within a given ecosystem.

Coastal ecosystem

Most coastal resource management projects adopted the following strategies to attain their objectives: (1) partnership with local government units, (2) multi-stakeholder involvement, (3) research-based program interventions, (4) a combination of technical and indigenous knowledge, and (5) hiring of local “experts”. Collectively, these strategies have helped increase community awareness on the importance of coastal resource protection and conservation and have promoted community involvement.

One outcome of coastal ecosystem projects is that community education and participation, combined with the implementation of needs-specific management strategies, have generally led to the maintenance and protection of the coral reefs – habitat to fish and marine life. This, in turn, has led to the successful re-population of particular fish species, and thereby increased the rates of fish catch. The success of most of these interventions depended, in large measure, on the support of the local communities, particularly the local fisherfolk, and the institutional support of local government agencies and officials in these communities.

Upland ecosystem

The common strategy adopted by most upland ecosystem projects was to emphasize integration of conservation and development approaches for sustainable natural resource management. Investment in social processes that could draw multi-stakeholder participation in all stages of the project made this integration possible. Capacity building and information, education and communication (IEC) campaigns have also been implemented to boost adoption of natural resource management technologies and livelihood projects in the project areas. Strategic interventions in these areas of capacity development have resulted in: (1) formation of people’s organizations (POs) and increased capacity of these organizations to manage community-based forest management projects, (2) increased number of community volunteers to safeguard protected areas, (3) increased vigilance in law enforcement in community-based forest management (CBFM) areas, and (4) increased corn production and income for farmers in agro-forestry projects.

Major constraints facing upland ecosystem programs

- ◆ *Socio-economic and resource conservation and protection activities are generally not integrated into the planning process.*
- ◆ *There is a dearth of alternative livelihood activities, especially for farmers during unfavorable climatic conditions.*
- ◆ *Natural resources management planning and decision-making are still based on administrative boundaries.*

Major constraints facing coastal ecosystem programs

- ◆ *Lack of integration of program delivery mechanisms*
- ◆ *Inadequate support and representation from the government and from local fisherfolks*
- ◆ *Unclear natural boundary delineation for holistic planning*
- ◆ *Lack of tenurial security (stewardship agreement) to encourage community management of mangroves*

In upland ecosystem cluster areas, the distinct technological interventions used included sloping agricultural land technology (SALT) for agro-forestry projects and the adoption of threat reduction analysis in biodiversity projects. This is a monitoring tool used to gauge the effectiveness of conservation interventions by measuring changes in the level of threats to biodiversity over time using a set of indicators (*FAO-UNDP-GEF Biodiversity Project, 2001*). An important lesson: projects within the upland ecosystem cluster in Bicol relied on trust building to gain people’s support for project implementation.

Watershed ecosystem

Common strategies adopted in watershed projects include: (1) multi-sectoral awareness campaigns, to ensure broad-based stakeholder participation in addressing issues confronting watershed ecosystem projects, (2) adoption of information, education and communication [IEC] approaches to promote awareness or to effect behavior change among affected communities, (3) establishment of linkages and partnerships between LGUs, POs and other stakeholders, and (4) the adoption of environment-friendly agricultural technologies.

Some of the strategic interventions used in projects under this cluster include: (1) the use of small water impounding structures such as supplemental irrigation for rainfed rice production, and (2) multi-sectoral development of the Naga River watershed. The river beautification and rehabilitation project has contributed to transforming the riverbank easement areas into a recreational park.

Lessons across ecosystems

Lessons across ecosystems refer to features consistently present and generally applicable to all three ecosystem clusters studied. The lessons that have emerged can be categorized into lessons that apply to *technology, participation, local governance, policy, and sustainability*. Each is crucial in the management of natural resources. They also present key binding elements in developing a holistic ecosystem management strategy.

Regardless of the ecosystem focus, the cases shared and reviewed during the workshop had shown that some degree of success can be achieved when these strategies are involved: (1) encouraging multi-stakeholder or multi-sectoral participation, (2) building partnerships with various groups, particularly with LGUs, (3) interventions that are people-centered and needs-based, (4) the integration of multiple project components, and (5) the use of indigenous knowledge and expertise.

Technology

Science-based and indigenous technologies are critical in sustaining natural resource management projects. During the workshop, participants recognized the processes of technology development, use, and adaptation as important dimensions of project sustainability. For example, appropriate ecological scale (such as upland, coastal, or watershed) must be used in analyzing the adaptability and fit of technologies to specific site situations and conditions. This requires establishing an appropriate monitoring and evaluation system, a research-based situation analysis and must be based on measurable goals. It should also include mechanisms for gauging the effectiveness of technologies employed and how these technologies may be further improved.

One common insight is that when stakeholders know how to use and monitor technological interventions, they tend to become more involved in the project. What this implies is that capacity building of stakeholders is equally important as a strategy for adapting technologies and technological innovation and scaling up their use. Furthermore, knowing how to use and monitor interventions enables stakeholders to modify and/or adapt conservation measures on their own as and when necessary.

Major constraints facing watershed ecosystem programs

- ◆ *Lack of an integrated approach that will reflect the interdependence among upland, lowland and coastal ecosystems*
- ◆ *Imbalance among environmental, economic and social objectives*
- ◆ *Project implementation and management is often co-terminus with the funding cycle, and therefore lacks continuity*

Factors affecting adaptation and application of technologies

- ◆ *Lack of structures and support mechanisms to take up technologies and replicate best practices*
- ◆ *Lack of market support for cash-based technology products such as peanuts, banana chips, etc.*
- ◆ *Lack of a complete technology package that addresses both poverty and the many different aspects of natural resource management*
- ◆ *Limited access of people's organizations to loans and credit facilities often essential to acquiring and maintaining new technologies*

Participation

There is increasing emphasis on multi-stakeholder participation in the planning and implementation of NRM programs and projects in the region. Across various ecosystem-based projects it was observed that the participation of multi-stakeholders in decision-making can reduce conflict, inefficiencies and misuse of resources, and can ensure that interventions undertaken are sustainable. For multi-stakeholder participation to be effective, however, the roles of each stakeholder must be clear at every stage of the process, starting from project planning and conceptualization.

Local people who have a direct stake in the management of natural resources are the most vulnerable group and should therefore be consulted early on, and must play an important role in the decision-making processes. Community participation and actions are anchored on people's recognition of the value of their natural resources, and the benefits they can derive from protecting and preserving these resources. It is also important to ensure that stakeholders have equal access to relevant information to elicit their active participation.

Local governance

Local government units (LGUs) are mandated to localize the application of Agenda 21 by undertaking and participating in sustainable area development initiatives. Several development agencies implementing projects in the region such as, the academe, non-government organizations and national government agencies (NGAs) have, as a result, forged partnerships with LGUs to implement Agenda 21.

Factors affecting good local governance

- ◆ *Lack of clarity in LGU and community roles in program development*
- ◆ *Lack of political will by some local authorities,*
- ◆ *Interference of partisan politics*
- ◆ *Lack of financial support from LGUs to undertake or sustain projects after it ends*
- ◆ *Limited involvement of communities in all project development processes*
- ◆ *Too much bureaucracy*

From the workshop, participants recognized the vital role that LGUs and people's organizations play in the success of natural resources management projects. The degree of effectiveness and efficiency of projects varied from individual project to province, city or municipality, depending on the commitment of the local chief executives, as well as the community stakeholders.

Factors affecting level of participation by stakeholders

- ◆ *Non-involvement of the relevant sectors in project planning and implementation*
- ◆ *Lack of practical schemes in the co-management of natural resources*
- ◆ *Limited participation by women and youth*

Local Agenda 21 states that each local authority should enter into a dialogue with its citizens, local organizations, and private enterprises and adopt 'a local Agenda 21'. Through consultation and consensus-building, local authorities would learn from citizens and from local, civic, community, business and industrial organizations and acquire the information needed for formulating the best strategies.

- Agenda 21, Chapter 28, sec 1. 3

The role and importance of local governance on sustainable use and management of natural resources has grown significantly following the adoption of Agenda 21 in 1992.

- Kjos, 1998; CADI, 2000

Projects in areas where an effective local governance system was in place, enjoyed a high degrees of transparency and accountability in all phases. LGUs would participate in projects they believed in or were convinced as being beneficial to people. While they have become aware of and sensitive to participatory development processes, LGUs still relied heavily on external rather than local expertise. This has often affected project sustainability. Participation and partnership arrangements with the local authorities can be strengthened through multi-stakeholder of management councils.

Policy

Policies, regulations and laws provide the essential frameworks in support of project implementation. While in some cases, the policy environment has served as a liberating force, in others it was seen as more of a constraint or barrier. Some laws and policies, especially the manner by which they were implemented, have not been able to ensure project success. Open access to resources, for instance, has made it difficult to curb unsustainable practices. Overlapping, inconsistent policies and the lack of effective inter-agency agreements and coordination have prevented the smooth implementation of natural resources management projects. New policies are therefore needed to support and sustain integrated watershed resource management interventions. For instance, policies mandating regular annual budget allocation from the LGU appropriations in support of local watershed programs have to be in place. To be effective, policies should be based upon sound research findings and must be supported by the community and LGU.

Factors affecting implementation of natural resource management policy

- ◆ *Lack of aggressive policy advocacy*
- ◆ *Weak implementation and enforcement of regulatory measures or policies*
- ◆ *Weak linkages between science, policy, and project management*
- ◆ *Weak linkages between research and natural resource management programs being implemented*
- ◆ *Lack of political will at the barangay and municipal levels to effectively protect and manage the natural resource base*

Factors affecting sustainability of natural resource management programs

- ◆ *Lack of a transition plan from implementing a mediated project to a community managing it*
- ◆ *Sustainability mechanisms, including phase out strategies not always built into project design*
- ◆ *Limited skills in resource generation and management*
- ◆ *Limited access of POs to loan or credit facilities*
- ◆ *Lack of appropriate monitoring and evaluation systems*
- ◆ *Lack of LGU financial support for environmental protection and maintenance*
- ◆ *Natural calamities and disasters, like the typhoons and cyclones that erode project gains*

Sustainability

Sustaining development interventions has always been the challenge in natural resource management. Focus and scale of sustainable efforts depend to a large extent on local conditions such as, existing resources, political dynamics, stakeholder actions, and unique features of the communities where NRM projects are being implemented.

Common lessons across various ecosystem-based projects show that factors like peace and order, an enabling policy environment, stable political conditions, and people's participation are crucial to project success and should guide project development and site selection. Where people's organizations or community-based organizations are formed, sustainability of project efforts and interventions tend to be ensured, especially if the project is implemented in partnership with LGUs. Also, small livelihood projects linked to local resources have a powerful impact on stakeholders based in the community. Best practices, recognized and shared, generate multiplier effect and add to sustainability of the interventions.

Developing an Integrated Watershed Management Framework for the Bicol Region

Sustainable development is “meeting the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs.”

– “Our Common Future.” The Brundtland Report, 1987

Challenges to overcome

Many challenges face the application of coastal, upland and watershed ecosystem- based approaches to address the complex issues of resource management linked to poverty alleviation initiatives in Bicol. Some of these challenges, it has been noted, are similar across different ecosystem approaches, while others are peculiar to a particular ecosystem. The workshop recognized the need for a new, innovative model or framework for effective natural resources management, given its important links to poverty. The participants recommended a shift toward a more “holistic, integrated ecosystem management approach” that can overcome challenges currently facing the region, characterized by the following conditions:

1. Existing program delivery mechanisms are not holistic and integrated according to the demands of an ecosystem approach. As the cases clearly indicate, more attention has been given to immediate economic gains more than long-term livelihood security or the resilience of the natural resource system to sustain productivity.
2. There is no clear natural system boundary for integrating program strategies in any of the ecosystem-based projects. Implementing agencies are more comfortable using political jurisdictions as the operating unit for interventions.
3. Support from the private sector, local communities, government units, and non-government organizations has not been adequate to maximize their potential contributions owing to varying capacities of these institutions as a result of their different backgrounds and orientations.
4. Issues of natural resource management cut across the ecosystem scales presently in use in the region. Thus, a system approach may be more broadly encompassing.
5. The project management cycle is often co-terminus with funding or with a political administration, and hence, projects lack continuity in operations.
5. The socio-economic objectives of projects are often not balanced with the environmental objectives of resource conservation and protection.
6. Broad-based awareness and support for sustainability mechanisms do not always exist. Often, implementing agencies and stakeholders are unclear about what they are supposed to sustain, whether it be projects, benefits, technologies or strategies.
7. Project or program designs are not always demand-driven, neither are they based on or responsive to local issues or needs.

An effective ecosystem approach to natural resources management is one that is holistic, where the entire ecosystem is used as the spatial context to make development and implementation decision about human activities involving land and water resources.

- UN Commission on Sustainable Development, 2000

Integrated watershed management as a basis for developing a holistic framework

The challenge in Bicol is to define appropriate approaches to addressing poverty while protecting a fast dwindling natural resource base. In contrast to other ecosystem types, the watershed has a well-defined natural boundary, and is thus easier to manage across spatial and time scales. For instance, upland communities, riparian areas, coastal areas, rivers, lakes and streams are critical natural features that affect the quantity and quality of water within a watershed. These features function as an ecosystem within a watershed. They can be 'nestled' within each other or within the watershed as a larger system.

Thus, integrated watershed management offers a superior approach to understanding the linkages between these systems and could be used to address, in a holistic fashion, the complex issues surrounding the natural resource base and human poverty.

In the experiences from Bicol shared during the workshop, the shift towards integrated watershed management can be built upon existing best practices and lessons learned.

Analyzing the case studies, participants identified the following essential elements of an integrated watershed management approach: (1) **multi-stakeholder participation** in all phases of project management, (2) **broad-based partnership arrangements**, which include stronger and more creative multi-agency and multi-disciplinary alliances and networks, (3) **result-oriented performance**, that balances socio-economic considerations with environmental objectives and outcomes, (4) **enabling policies**, (5) **process-oriented approaches**, employing a *systems approach* to problem solving, (6) **multi-level and multi-stakeholder capacity building**, and (7) **broad and stable funding sources** for IWM projects and programs.

Shift towards integrated watershed management: Implications and recommended actions

For each of the elements outlined above, the workshop identified a number of implications and recommended action points.

Multi-stakeholder participation

Implications	Recommended actions
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Active participation of various stakeholders in all phases and processes of IWM programs and projects is required. This demands deeper commitment for all stakeholders to sustain project efforts and benefits. Participation of communities and LGUs is indispensable to the success and sustainability of IWM programs and projects. The capacities of these stakeholders should be strengthened to prepare them to take over the roles and responsibilities for local governance. Multi-sectoral participation should result in convergence of services towards human ecological security. Defining and legislating the roles and functions of stakeholders (communities, LGUs, LGAs, and others) can result in stronger inter-institutional participation. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Conduct an information, education and communication (IEC) drive to the concerned local chief executives to disseminate the outcome and lessons from this workshops. Greater collaboration between and among agencies involved in watershed programs is needed. Develop mechanisms to encourage maximum multi-sectoral participation.

Broad-based partnership arrangements

Implications	Recommended actions
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ IWM requires a broad perspective in problem identification. Concerned agencies representing various sectors must be able to plot a common direction towards IWM. ▪ Need for strong and active networking, alliance building and collaboration with multi-disciplinary and multi-sectoral stakeholders. ▪ Need for research-based management approaches to be able to deal with the changing interaction between human and natural systems. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Create a technical working group to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ identify areas of collaboration between and among agencies involved in IWM, ○ establish mechanisms of collaboration, and ○ prepare terms of reference and memorandum of agreements / memorandum of understanding to formalize partnerships. ▪ Identify existing management structures in potential project areas. ▪ Conduct consultative meetings with LGUs, chief executives and watershed stakeholders. ▪ Identify potential partners at the LGU level. ▪ Link relevant peoples' organizations to LGUs.

Result-oriented performance

Implications	Recommended actions
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Need to balance socio-economic objectives with environmental objectives, as well as their outcomes. ▪ Need to address long-term livelihood security as opposed to immediate food security. ▪ Need to institute appropriate monitoring and evaluation systems where measurable goals, effects of interventions, roles and responsibilities of various stakeholders can be periodically assessed. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Publish success stories or best practices on natural resources management. ▪ Identify acceptable outputs and indicators of IWM projects. ▪ IIRR, together with multi-sectoral partners, promote IWM approaches and initiatives that have worked. ▪ Publish workshop proceedings and provide copies to workshop participants.

Enabling policies

Implications	Recommended actions
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Paradigm shift to IWM implies corresponding policy shifts and harmonization with existing relevant policies. It also demands some changes in existing government structures, requiring simplified, less bureaucratic procedures and processes. ▪ New policies to have the 'force of law' should be translated into executive orders or congressional action. ▪ There is a need to have clear-cut policies at all levels of project implementation (national, regional, and local). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Initiate review of existing policies relevant to IWM in the Bicol region. ▪ Work out LGU resolutions concerning the acceptability and adaptability of watershed programs in specific areas. ▪ Clarify the roles/functions of the NGAs and the LGUs concerning IWM implementation. ▪ Formulate a resolution for the integration of watershed management approaches in agriculture sector programs.

Process-oriented approaches

Implications	Recommended actions
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ IWM recognizes a systems approach, and should therefore look at systems and sub-systems that make up a watershed. ▪ For greater project impact, priority should be given to the identification of critical watershed areas in the Bicol region. Focus all necessary resources to these important areas. ▪ Watershed boundaries should be well defined and divided into micro-watersheds to ensure manageability. ▪ IWM project strategy should include the following components: IEC, capacity building, policy advocacy, monitoring and evaluation, inter-disciplinary assistance/expertise, networking and alliance building, conflict resolution strategies, and integration of agricultural and environmental development approaches. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Identify priority critical watershed areas in the Bicol region. ▪ Promote and disseminate field-tested and location-specific technologies through IEC support materials and regular lesson sharing workshops. ▪ Terms of reference of concerned agencies should be defined prior to starting any project. ▪ Define integrated strategic intervention covering conservation and protection of natural resources and sustainable livelihood of local communities. ▪ Develop framework and parameters for site-specific IWM, which will be the basis for coming up with regional and local IWM plans. ▪ Develop simple monitoring and evaluation tools. Include outside (external) evaluators.

Multi-level and multi-stakeholder capacity building

Implications	Recommended actions
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Capacity building is a critical step in an IWM approach. It should be focused to <i>de facto</i> managers and stakeholders at the LGU and local levels. ▪ Capacity building should put emphasis on values orientation and hands-on exercises to encourage greater participation and enhanced learning. ▪ Capacity building for IWM requires commitment and support from various sectors, particularly from POs, LGUs and NGOs. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Conduct training needs analysis of various stakeholders in IWM, particularly of LGUs and POs. ▪ Develop a training plan in consultation with concerned stakeholders. ▪ Provide continuing education to POs. ▪ Key institutions should provide training to concerned stakeholders.

Table 2 Multi-stakeholder capacity building

This involves capacity building on the various aspects of integrated watershed management for key watershed stakeholders, including communities around the watershed, the private sector, LGU personnel, government and non-government resource managers.

Some recognized training needs of stakeholders

- ◆ *integrated watershed management*
- ◆ *environmental laws*
- ◆ *participatory approaches*
- ◆ *project phase-over mechanisms*
- ◆ *conflict management*
- ◆ *participatory monitoring and evaluation*
- ◆ *forest fire prevention*
- ◆ *resource management*
- ◆ *environment performance monitoring*
- ◆ *value of stewardship*
- ◆ *sense of ownership of projects*

Broad and stable funding sources

Implications	Recommended actions
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> An IWM approach requires adequate financial resources. Co-sharing of resources is required to maximize desired IWM results. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Solicit possible fund source to sustain an IWM program. Identify/facilitate linkage to funding agencies (sources of resources). Build on network of donors. Adopt a centralized conduit for fund raising for IWM programs in the region.

Proposed operational framework for integrated watershed management in the Bicol region

Four operational phases and corresponding sets of recommended actions have been also identified as crucial to the success of IWM initiatives in the Bicol region.

Entry phase

Aim	Recommended actions
<p>Also known as the <i>pre-watershed development phase</i>, and aims to establish trust and partnership with communities and stakeholders in the watershed, as well as to create awareness on poverty and natural resources management issues and problems.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Establish criteria for the selection of watershed community sites, including parameters for feasibility studies. Conduct literature review and studies on what have and have not worked. Review existing data on poverty and natural resources situation, including pertinent laws, regulations, ordinances, agreements (at international, national, regional and local levels). Identify key stakeholders; define their roles, responsibilities and capabilities. Identify major resource management issues or opportunities upon which initial dialogue and consensus building could be based.

Preparatory phase

Aim	Recommended actions
<p>Also known as the <i>planning phase</i>, and aims to develop a comprehensive watershed plan that is community-based, with the participation of concerned stakeholders.</p> <p><i>Processes during the preparatory phase could include watershed community immersion, transect walk, rural appraisal, dialogues, community assemblies, and processing and validation of priority secondary data through consultations.</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ Conduct consultation meetings with local communities and stakeholders to further clarify roles and responsibilities.▪ Conduct participatory watershed resources assessment, problem identification and prioritization.▪ Identify or create a watershed management council.▪ Identify and prioritize applicable or useful participatory technology.▪ Develop a comprehensive watershed plan.▪ Conduct multi-level training needs assessment for communities and other stakeholders.

Implementation phase

Aim	Recommended actions
<p>Also known as the <i>action phase</i> and aims to facilitate the process of community and multi-stakeholder participation in implementing actions for watershed resources development and management.</p> <p><i>In selecting technologies for application, those based on research developed by universities and agricultural colleges are preferred, along with time-tested indigenous knowledge and local innovations.</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ Establish institutional mechanisms for partnership and co-management of resources with various sectors (local government, communities, non-government organizations, private sector, etc.).▪ Formulate or lobby for the formulation of enabling legislation and policies.▪ Use/apply local and indigenous knowledge.▪ Adopt a learning approach for knowledge and skills building of participating stakeholders.▪ Establish multi-sectoral/disciplinary monitoring and evaluation committee.▪ Application of a systems approach.▪ Research-based (adaptive) management systems.▪ Incorporation of tested technologies, both research-based and indigenous technologies.▪ Multi-level, multi-stakeholder capacity building.

Turn-over phase

Aim	Recommended actions
<p>Also known as the <i>withdrawal phase</i>, and aims to consolidate watershed resource management program achievements by further developing capabilities of watershed communities and evolving local resource management institutions towards full self-reliance and sustainability.</p> <p><i>Sustainability of IWM programs in the region can be ensured through:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Creation of environment management unit at all levels of the local government;</i> • <i>Co-management agreement for inter-LGU watershed protection and development;</i> • <i>Formation of resources user's associations; and</i> • <i>Federation of people's organizations for watershed resources management.</i> 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Strengthen partnership and co-management of watershed management projects with communities, non-government organizations, private sector, and LGUs for long-term sustainability. ▪ Establish linkage and network alliance of multi-sectoral stakeholders. ▪ Initiate memorandum of agreement (MOA) for all partners and/or stakeholders. ▪ Conduct multi-sectoral sustainability planning and capacity building for all stakeholders. ▪ Formulate and implement tenurial instruments or other mechanisms that promote equity and access to resources.

Strengthening monitoring and evaluation systems

Given the crucial role of monitoring and evaluation in the success of any program, workshop participants identified key parameters for assessing performance of IWM interventions in the region. The parameters point to elements of good governance, partnership, participation, impact and sustainability measures, and are outlined in question form in Table 3.

Table 3 Elements and parameters of a M & E System for IWM

Elements of performance
Is there good local governance?
Is partnership inclusive and broad-based? Did it result in effective service delivery?
How do we measure sustainability? What are we trying to sustain – project, technology, or benefits?
Is there active participation of various stakeholders?
Are project/program approaches responsive?
How do we determine project impact? How do we measure if the project is able to improve the quality of life of stakeholders?
Are there mechanisms for integrating project components across watershed scale including appropriate institutional arrangements and linkages?

Moving Forward

The 'environment' is where we all live, and 'development' is what we all do in attempting to improve our lot within that abode.

– Background to “Our Common Future,” The Brundtland Report. 1987

An integrated watershed management approach has long been recognized and advocated by informed sectors in the region as the most promising and holistic approach to alleviating poverty in Bicol while managing its natural resource base. Without a clearly defined operational framework for integrating and complementing programs, efforts to address the twin problems of poverty and resource degradation in the region would remain largely ineffective. The sectoral inclination of various resource management agencies remains, however, to be one of the greatest challenges to making the leap towards IWM. Lessons that have emerged from the case studies have reinforced the need for more integrated management actions using watershed as a common unit of planning, action and service delivery.

Issues and questions

The workshop participants believe that the shift to IWM can help address poverty while managing and sustaining the natural resources of the Bicol region. They also weighed their readiness to take on an IWM approach based on lessons gained from the workshop. In assessing implications posed by a shift to IWM, the participants raised some issues that need to be addressed and resolved in future discussions and workshops.

1. Is there supporting policy direction from the government towards integrated watershed management?
2. What do we really want to see on the ground when we define an operational framework?
3. How do we define the roles of various stakeholders within a watershed?

4. How prepared are the stakeholders to take up integrated watershed management?
5. How do we ensure success of an IWM approach, when single strategy programs in the past have found difficulty achieving success?

The development of an IWM operational framework is in no way complete. This workshop and learning process has been a logical step forward in the effort to put integrated watershed resources management in action. The stakeholders should collectively determine how to move forward, building on the lessons synthesized from the workshop. IIRR and its partners intend to share the results of this project to a broader group of audiences so that the framework may be further tested and refined. IIRR also intends to further validate its results with the most critical and vulnerable stakeholders, the rural people. A series of needs-based, capacity-building activities on integrated watershed management approaches will be conducted to critical stakeholders in pilot areas in the region to enable them to manage more sustainably their natural resources.

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Annex 1

Case summaries ¹

¹ For the full text of the case summaries, please contact the authors (see directory for contact numbers and addresses).

Coastal environment program implementation in Prieto Diaz, Sorsogon, Philippines: Insights into coastal resources co-management

Pobleo M. Florece, Rebecca R. Matusalem, and Ruby L. Mendones

The Coastal Environment Program (CEP) in Prieto Diaz started in August 1993 with the objective to protect, conserve, rehabilitate and manage mangroves, sea grasses and coral reefs in 11 coastal villages through the community-based approach. CEP was the outcome of a DENR administrative order which took effect in April 1993. The aim of the larger program was to rehabilitate, protect, conserve and manage the country's coastal resources, employing stakeholders-based principles of sustainable development. CEP policy emphasizes partnership of all sectors, especially the local communities, to protect the coastal ecosystems and ensure equitable access and sustainable use of natural resources.

Components and strategies

The project has four main components: (1) community organizing; (2) information, education and communication; (3) resource assessment and inventory; and (4) alternative livelihood. A mangrove stewardship agreement (MSA), renewable every 25 years, was used as a tenurial instrument to ensure effective protection and sustainable management of mangrove forests in Prieto Diaz.

Processes adopted

The CEP forged partnership with several local organizations, institutions, people's organizations, NGOs, LGUs at municipal and barangay levels, and the Bureau of Fisheries and Aquatic Resources (BFAR). An inventory and assessment of coastal resources in the area - coral reefs, sea grasses, mangrove stand, birds and fauna, were conducted to gather information on current status and to determine appropriate management interventions.

Community organizing processes were employed to identify core community problems and opportunities and capacity building needs of villagers. Training in areas specific to the project's and the community's needs was conducted, including values reorientation, leadership formation, and cooperatives and skills development for alternative livelihood.

Radio broadcast, print and film media supplemented by school visits constituted the information, education and communication (IEC) component of the project. Alternative livelihoods were also explored to uplift the economic conditions of the coastal communities while shifting community members away from illegal livelihood activities such as cutting of mangroves, blast fishing, cyanide fishing, etc. Shell craft, crab culture and fattening, goat raising, seaweed farming, nipa plantation, fish vending and prawn culture were some of the alternative livelihood explored.

Results

The CEP program in Prieto Diaz was turned over to the local government and the people's organization in 1995. In 1998, the project received the best coastal resources management project award. Various program strategies such as promotion of environment-friendly technologies, expansion of livelihood opportunities have protected and improved area's coastal resources.

Lessons learned

An evaluation conducted in 2002 reflected a moderately stable people's organization in charge of the CEP, but with aging officers as potential future setback. To enhance program sustainability, a second-line of officers was recommended to be developed through an electoral system to ensure that the organization attracts the right members.

Initiatives on sustainable capiz fishery: The case of San Miguel Bay

Ronald B. Lachica

Capiz (*placuna placenta*), a laterally flat, circular marine shell found in Philippine estuaries and noted for its unique aesthetic properties such as luster, transparency and smoothness, is a popular item as glazed windows and home decor and a source of livelihood in many Philippine fishing towns. Concern has been raised in recent years over the sharp decline in the production of capiz and the declining number of capiz beds in Philippine waters. Depletion has been particularly evident in San Miguel Bay in Southern Luzon, significantly reducing harvest and adversely affecting the livelihood of local fisherfolk, capiz buyers and manufacturers. At stake over the long term — unless immediate conservation and management measures are undertaken — is the capiz population and its byproducts.

Components and strategies

Haribon Foundation implemented a Capiz Fishery Management and Conservation Project in Calabanga, one of seven coastal municipalities bordering San Miguel Bay, in September 1998 with funding support from B&Q of U.K. Program components include community-based coastal resource management (CBCRM) as key strategy, capitalizing on partnerships with multiple stakeholders in the community such as, the fisherfolk, local government units, including barangay officials, academic institutions, the Fisheries and Aquatic Resource Management Council (FARMC), and the church sector.

Four main components of the project include community organizing, community education, research and resource management, networking and lobbying. To build a pool of committed community leaders, the Samahang Maliliit na Mangingisda ng Bonot-Sta. Rosa (SMMSR), a community organization, was formed.

Processes adopted

Among the processes to promote the project and raise awareness and support for the conservation efforts include community organizing and community education. Target groups included fisherfolk, local governments, including barangay officials, all other stakeholders previously identified.

Market research, policy formulation and enforcement, information dissemination, stakeholder consultation on policies, and surveillance and prosecution of violators were also undertaken. Networking and lobbying formed part of the process to build broad-based project support.

Results

An ordinance to protect and conserve capiz was approved by the Sangguniang Bayan of Calabanga; a monitoring team composed of capiz collectors and buyers, fisherfolk, NGOs and the LGU of Calabanga conducted research, monitoring and surveillance, and apprehended illegal trawlers. Alternative income sources among fisherfolk, such as freshwater tilapia culture, establishment of stationary left net (parigid), handicraft and culture of siganid in pens and cages were also explored, with tilapia culture gaining success and therefore, popular acceptance.

Lessons learned

Success of fishery management and conservation initiatives depends, in large measure, on multi-stakeholder support. Livelihood initiatives should come from the community. Policy should be backed by research, in addition to multi-stakeholder support.

Managing “*badoy*” fisheries of Sorsogon Bay: Challenges to effective interface of roles of academe, LGU and local community

Rommel R. Dioneda Sr. and Victor S. Soliman

Sorsogon Bay hosts diverse marine life that include finfishes, crustaceans, mollusks, including the short-necked clam called *badoy* (*Paphia undulate*). A shallow fishing ground, the Bay has however been heavily over-fished, its marine life maximally harvested sometimes beyond regenerative levels. This project, led by the Bicol University under its Bicol Fish Biodiversity Program (BFBIODEV), provides scientific basis to manage the *badoy* clams and other marine life in the Sorsogon Bay.

Components and strategies

(1) Management through regulation (2) Advocacy through information campaigns (IEC) (3) Research in support of scientific management, including indigenous knowledge (4) Government-NGO-PO (communities)-Academe interphase in all aspects of the project.

Processes adopted

Regulations adopted include: continuing ban on compressor fishing, setting size limits to the Bay’s catch to ensure their maturation and spawning before harvest, effective licensing of fisheries with preference to local or residential fishers is being proposed since the biggest violators of the compressor fishing ban are ‘outsiders’. Size imposition on catch is enforced by the buyers themselves, but the strategy becomes ineffective when catch are not returned to their habitat but are instead resold. IEC advocacy campaign was directed at fishers during monthly sampling gatherings. Comprehensive study on *badoy* biology, ecology, fisheries is being pursued to guide its scientific management.

Results

The clam follows a cycle of collapse and rebound. The first comprehensive stock assessment in 1999 revealed underexploitation. Aside from clam resilience, enforcement of regulation and loose compliance contributed to the positive trend. Studies recommend continuance of regulation until such time that comprehensive information on *badoy* biology, ecology and fisheries can guide its scientific management. A unified fishery ordinance is in effect in six Bay municipalities.

Lessons learned

Regulations have impact, but nature has its own built-in regulation (such as “red tide”). “Management” tends to bar people from the resource, therefore alternative livelihood is crucial. Important also are health risk awareness on certain practices, monitoring and enforcement, and support IEC to these advocacies. Fisherfolks long fishing experience provides rich indigenous knowledge. Science must complement fishers’ traditional knowledge in the search for answers. Though regulatory laws exist, close monitoring ensures enforcement. Avenues to harmonize science and culture and foster community-supported management must be improved. There is need to effectively interface GO-NGO-PO-academe mandates in the resource’s management.

Reviving the stock of sinarapan, the “world’s smallest commercial fish”: Adapting biodiversity conservation and co-community science application

Victor S. Soliman and Antonino B. Mendoza, Jr.

Ford Motor Company-Philippines through a Ford Conservation and Environment grant provided technical assistance to the Bicol University to implement the Sinarapan Repopulation Strategy (SRS) project. SRS was seen as concrete action to revive the stock of the ‘world’s smallest commercial fish; which had become nearly extinct from overfishing by fishing gear and predation by tilapias. The project to revive Sinarapan in Lake Buhi protects and manages the stock in the mountain lakes, as they are source for live fish transfers. As a rallying symbol for biodiversity conservation, a viable fish population in the mountain lakes should be supported by a strong network of protection by community residents, local executives and indigenous Aetas.

Components and strategies

SRS is a co-community science scheme for biodiversity conservation. Major SRS phases include (1) site suitability assessment, (2) live fish transfers, and (3) stock and environmental monitoring. Aside from technical aspects, SRS had adopted other strategies such as building partnerships with government and other stakeholders, research on fish biology and population dynamics, information dissemination and capacity building.

Processes adopted

Stakeholders were involved in several project stages: the local government and concerned barangay residents took part in consultations during site assessment and project planning and actively participated in transferring live fish from Lake Manapao to Lake Katugday. Local government councils supported policy measures to revive and protect the Sinarapan.

Results

San Ramon Barangay Council passed a resolution declaring Lake Makuwaw a Sinarapan sanctuary and provided administrative and management support. The resolution was submitted to the Buhi Sangguniang Bayan so that a municipal ordinance could be formulated.

In November 2001, during regular lake monitoring, the BU research team obtained from Lake Buhi a very low Sinarapan density (1%) from a total of some 500 fish individuals of various species in selected sampling stations in Lake Buhi — an improvement from the previous years’ samplings. While the repopulation strategy appears to be succeeding and Sinarapan can now be found in Lake Buhi, the challenge to bring back Buhi’s wonder fish remains.

Lessons learned

Experiences in implementing the SRS confirmed that science is not solely the domain of formal scientists and researchers. Indigenous knowledge can provide insightful ideas worthy to pursue. Local government support is indispensable to biodiversity protection and management. Pro-active information dissemination to local government councils is also a key strategy to gain cooperation for conservation. Corollary to this, political will for biodiversity conservation can be enhanced with regular and vigilant information campaigns among local executives.

San Miguel Island marine fishery reserve: Lessons on local governance and co-management, Tabaco City

Victor S. Soliman

Endowed with vast coral reefs, seagrass beds and mangroves, San Miguel Island Bay in the Lagonoy is source of food and income for its 7,000 inhabitants. The island's basic economy is fishing; any stresses to the marine habitats are therefore a prime concern.

Preparatory activities for the establishment of a marine fishery reserve in San Miguel was funded by the Bicol University from 1995-1997. In 1998, a municipal ordinance formally established the 2.25-sq m San Miguel Marine Fishery Reserve (SMI-MFR). The Tabaco City government and the *Sagurong Barangay* Council started contributing to its maintenance in 1998. In 2002, SMI-MFR was recognized by PhilReefs as the "Second Best-Managed Coral Reef in the Philippines." To date it is one of 14 actively operating marine reserves in the Bicol region.

Components and strategies

(1) Partnership with academe and the local government, (2) Regular evaluation by stakeholders, (3) Stakeholders' participation during consultations for the establishment of the MFR, (4) technical assessments of the capture fisheries and coastal habitats, (5) Involvement and capacity-building of the MFR Management Council (MC), a people's organization with annual funding support from the city government manages and protects the MFR, and (6) Regular co-community monitoring of fish stock.

Processes adopted

Stakeholder participation started in 1995, before SMI was declared a protected area. Throughout the different phases, the local government made significant funding and technical assistance contributions. The MC and fisherfolks helped formulate the guidelines for public test fishing, a tool for fish stock monitoring.

Mechanisms to sustain managing the reserve include: (1) regular LGU fund allocation and policy support, and (2) continuing education and capability building for MC and fisherfolk on effective MFR management and fish monitoring.

Results

Indicators of success: (1) increased fish catch rate at the SMI-MFR from 1995-2001; (2) replication of MFR in the municipal waters of neighboring coastal towns; (3) positive perception by the community of MFR as marine sanctuary management approach; (4) return of rare fish and marine species in the sanctuary; (5) strong LGU support and activity community participation in the resource's management; and (6) more students from the communities now taking courses in fisheries and aquaculture.

Lessons learned

Partnership with all stakeholders has provided the social bond vital in drawing out cooperation from as many sectors for the project, with the local management council providing the most influence in managing the reserve. Legal basis such as MOUs create the formal structure but by itself is inadequate without popular support. Information campaigns and advocacy are thus crucial to establishing this support and sustaining it. In working with the LGUs, the most vital lesson was: show results first and funding support from the LGUs will come. Other vital lessons: excellent results are achieved by maintaining project integrity and staff commitment; public test fishing has been effective in demonstrating impact of marine protection and conservation.

Community-based resource protection program: Mt. Isarog Natural Park

Crisostomo S. Rivero and Jocelyn A. Nique

For decades, Mt. Isarog Natural Park in Camarines Sur, one of the first components of the National Integrated Protected Areas System (NIPAS) in the Philippines, was hounded by threats of conversion of its forests to agriculture, timber poaching, overhunting of its wildlife for livelihood, mono-cropping along forest fringes and overall biodiversity disturbance from unregulated tourism and human activities. To address these threats, DENR and CARE-Philippines undertook the Community-Based Resource Protection Program (CBRPP) at Mt. Isarog. The Program aims to minimize illegal activities in the protected area, enforcing conservation laws as main focus of intervention.

Components and strategies

The project has two main components: (1) organization and effective deployment of regular DENR personnel and CARE-assisted rangers in the protected area, collectively termed as the special action team or SAT, and (2) organization, training and mobilization of community-based volunteer groups referred to as the Mt. Isarog Guardians or MIGs.

Processes adopted

The Protected Area Management Board (PAMB) represented by the LGU, PO, government agencies, NGOs and indigenous communities are the project's major stakeholders including community volunteers and project implementers from DENR and CARE-Philippines.

Stakeholder participation was a prime consideration in the formation and composition of the forest protection volunteer groups, and in formulating guidelines for MIG member selection. The MIGs participated in a series of capacity building, organizational strengthening, and forest protection training activities.

At the end of CARE project's support in 2004, funds for park protection activities will come from the different government agencies, and POs to which the teams are attached, and from income generating projects. Support to the CBRPP has been facilitated through: (1) barangay development planning and consultations, (2) assistance from the private sector and political leaders, and (3) by involving the MIGs in activities to improve their knowledge and skills.

Results

Expected outputs of the program, such as the formation of the SAT and mobilization of MIGs have been achieved. Vigilance of the MIGs has improved monitoring, reporting and action on illegal activities at the Park. The project has also: (1) inculcated a sense of responsibility among MIG members, (2) facilitated transfer of knowledge and skills from project implementers to the community, and (3) provided a venue for meaningful interaction among various stakeholders in the conservation efforts.

Lessons learned

Information dissemination, wider participation from the community and available logistic and technical support all contributed to the project's success. The positive effects of previous IEC campaigns by Haribon Foundation and the National Integrated Protected Areas Program sustained the project. One important lesson is that roles of various stakeholders should be defined and clarified before project implementation. Some Filipino values such as the *padrino* (patronage) system worked against the selection of qualified MIG members. But a more effective forest protection monitoring and reporting system was devised. One important lesson: channeling funds to the MIG could best be facilitated by volunteers from established community-based organizations.

Community-based forest resource management project, Tible, Sipocot, Camarines Sur

Vivencio M. Cabanayan and Angelito I. Rutaquio

The community-based forest management project (CBFM) is part of a broader natural resources management program (NRMP) funded by the United States Agency for International Development (USAID) in 1996, one of the first donor-funded initiatives to implement a Philippines strategy for sustainable development and a 25-Year Master Plan for Forestry Development. The goal of NRMP is to encourage ecologically-sound, long-term economic growth focused on management of the country's tropical forests, biodiversity, and improvement of forestry-related industries. In Bicol, NRMP was implemented in Tible, Sipocot in Camarines Sur; and San Pascual, Basud and Pambuhan, Mercedes in Camarines Norte.

Components and strategies

The program has four components: (1) natural resources management, (2) organizational management, (3) livelihood, and (4) support services.

Processes adopted

Tible Bantay Kalikasan Organization, Inc. (TIBKOI) was formed to plan, implement and manage the activities of the project. TIBKOI is registered with the Securities and Exchange Commission (SEC), enabling this people's organization to enter into a community forest management agreement with the DENR for the protection and management of 1,954 ha of forest land. NRM activities include establishment seedling nurseries, agroforestry farm expansion, reforestation of open areas, sustainable harvesting of matured trees and community involvement in forest protection and management. The project's organizational management component included activities in information and education, strengthening self-help groups (*Saknungan* and *Bayanihan*), project management and fund sourcing. A credit and saving scheme and a consumer store were established to support the livelihood needs of the community. Capital build-up for credit and savings were derived from members' contributions and timber harvesting and contracting arrangements.

Results

Illegal forestry activities in the area have been reduced by 50% and continues to decrease. Members and nonmembers have shifted to farming and other alternative livelihood activities. Community members have also actively participated in regular environment performance monitoring. Many of the PO members have been empowered through capability building and have acquired basic management skills and the confidence to run for local public office. The community now enjoys basic utilities such as electricity, water and irrigation, health services, and good roads.

Lessons learned

Lack of an effective information program and insufficient manpower have limited the implementation of a resource use plan and has abetted violations of the CBFM agreement, suspending the harvest of matured trees. Furthermore, lack of adequate market planning for farm produce has led to surplus production and consequently, low farm gate prices for the farmers. However, these problems can be addressed through better planning and technical assistance.

Mt. Bulusan Volcano Natural Park: Community-based resources management

Aydelfe M. Salvador and Caroline Manguiat - Ubalde

The 3,673 ha Mt. Bulusan Natural Park nestles the pristine 16-ha Bulusan Lake and traverses 20 barangays of the adjoining municipalities of Casiguran, Irosin, Bulusan, Juban and Barcelona in Sorsogon. It is the watershed enclave of the five municipalities, where the *barangays* draw their water needs. The Park is habitat to diverse flora and fauna.

The Park's rich resources have deteriorated from forest resource extraction and unsustainable upland farming, the root cause of which is poverty. Practices like slash and burn agriculture and rampant tree cutting account for at least 1,000 trees felled from the Park every year.

Components and strategies

The project has four components: community organizing, livelihood development, resource management, and advocacy. Community organizing focuses on strengthening upland dwellers groups to effectively and efficiently manage the Park. The livelihood component improves the socioeconomic condition of the Park communities through alternative and sustainable livelihood compatible with protection and conservation. The resource development component promotes sustainable agriculture and conservation-based interventions, such as installing forest guards and monitoring Park biodiversity. Partnerships and linkages with stakeholders are strengthened by advocacy.

Processes adopted

LIKAS, in partnership with the Foundation for the Philippine Environment, conducted a study using rapid site assessment methods to determine the area's biodiversity and the impact of nearby communities. A multisectoral workshop attended by community leaders, NGOs, POs, LGUs, and regional and national government agencies validated result of the biodiversity inventory as basis to develop a site-focused Park program.

Nine of 20 barangays around the Park, where the degree of encroachment and livelihood potential are greatest, were selected to implement the program. Appropriate interventions and strategies were designed through the community resource assessment. A research team from the barangays was formed and trained in community resource analysis and planning. To manage the park sustainably, a federation of POs, the *Pederasyon ng Nagkaisang Samahan ng Bundok Bulusan* (PNAGSAMA), was formed.

Results

Program actions resulted in a viable and autonomous federation of POs, a more diversified alternative livelihood base, increased income for farmers (from PhP1,507-3,500/mo.), raised awareness of the communities of environmental laws, and collective action. Strategic partnership between LGUs and the PO federation were also forged. Through advocacy and lobbying at the LGU level, honoraria of barangay-accredited *Bantay-Gubat* or Forest Guards were included in the annual municipal and *barangay* budgets.

Lessons learned

Implementing biodiversity conservation is a complex issue. Interrelated factors of environmental, socio-economic, political and other pressures need to be addressed. Building strong people's organizations is critical to sustainability. Choice of livelihood project should consider compatibility with economic development and conservation. Financial sustainability remains a concern. Concrete advocacy plans need to create awareness at all levels. Regular funds must be allocated and appropriate policy support enacted.

Mt. Masaraga agroforestry pilot project

Antonio P. Payonga, Jerry S. Bigornia and Jeffrey Sapillar

The farmers of Mt. Masaraga have been practicing "slash and burn" farming for more than three decades. Some farmers have also encroached the watershed reserve and converted portions of the forest to agricultural uses. This has caused serious and interrelated problems of soil fertility loss, erosion and low crop yields.

From 1986 to 1990, the Bicol University College of Agriculture and Agroforestry (BUCAF) implemented the Mt. Masaraga Agroforestry Pilot Project in Sitio Parina, Balogo, Oas, Albay with USAID support.

Components and strategies

Among project strategies used were: (1) livelihood assistance to upland farmers, (2) soil and water conservation techniques, (3) civil infrastructure works such as farm-to-market roads construction, and (4) capacity building for farmers on crop and animal production, alley cropping system, and leadership training. The strategies for the adoption of technology were enhanced through the development of model farms and conduct of training for local people in the project site. All training was experiential and hands-on. Project staff were also required to stay in the site to establish regular communication and build closer ties with the community.

Processes adopted

The BUCA, DENR, DA, DAR, LGU represented by *barangay* officials and the corn growers were the project stakeholders. They were consulted about their roles during project conceptualization and planning. Government and *barangay* representatives also participated in the assessment of Mt. Masaraga watershed and in the socio-economic survey. Stakeholders participated from problem diagnosis to monitoring and evaluation.

Results

The project was able to establish 150ha of upland farms using soil and water technology combined with the sloping agriculture land technology system. This resulted in: (1) increase in corn grain yield by as much as 43%-186%, (2) production of various crops due to bench terraces formed by leguminous tree hedgerows, and (3) reduction of commercial fertilizer input as soil nutrients were gradually recovered. Building strong relationships among stakeholders facilitated technology adoption.

Lessons learned

Previous negative experience with other development workers made the participants hesitant at first to adopt a new technology. But when they did, training of farmer technicians helped improve their skills and participation in adopting technology. Technology, however, should not be considered as a "cure-all" prescription. Staying at the project site and establishing rapport with the people also helped improve farmer participation in the project. A system of rewards and incentives to farmers worked to enhance farmer participation.

Reduction of direct threats to biodiversity: An alternative measure of success of conservation initiatives for Mt. Isarog Natural Park

Esteban Paga, Alexander D. Nayve and Roy Layosa

While Mt. Isarog harbors rich biodiversity and is one of the most important watersheds in Camarines Sur, this important resource is rapidly being lost due to multifarious problems related to poverty. To save what remains of its biodiversity, CARE-Philippines implemented a five-year project (1999-2004) called Sustainable Management of Mt. Isarog's Territories (SUMMIT).

Components and strategies

As a strategy to achieve the biodiversity conservation objective of SUMMIT, threat reduction analysis (TRA) was adopted as a tool to measure the success of multi-stakeholder biodiversity conservation initiatives for Mt. Isarog.

Information about the TRA strategy was downloaded from the Internet by project staff midway through the project and adopted and piloted in nine sites within the Park after a series of validation and consultation workshops with the various stakeholders. In the context of TRA, success is measured in terms of the reduction of direct threats to biodiversity.

Processes adopted

Stakeholders involved in the TRA process included the local development councils, community-based organizations, people's organizations, tribal groups, citizens, project staff, NGOs and national government agencies. They participated in the preparation of a site assessment map, in listing and prioritizing threats to biodiversity, and in the formulation and implementation of strategies and action points to reduce those threats.

To sustain this strategy, the project continues to develop the capacity of the multi-sectoral and multi-disciplinary TRA management team, and pursues partnership with the local government to adopt the technology and to provide regular budget allocation.

Results

Of 20 direct threats to biodiversity identified using the TRA, one threat was addressed and completely eliminated and 10 were significantly reduced. Most of the unmitigated threats were those perpetrated by outsiders and those related to agricultural expansion to the forest fringes.

Lessons learned

Recurrence and ascendancy of threats will remain unabated when interventions are piecemeal. Interventions geared directly to the reduction of threats will be meaningless without addressing the vulnerability or denial of rights of perpetrators, composed mostly of poor and vulnerable families. Participation of stakeholders in threat reduction management has become more intense once they begin to appreciate the value of interventions. One of the keys to sustainability of TRA lies in the LGU's willingness to allocate annual budget for its continuing implementation.

Local resource management project in Arimbay, Legazpi City

Ma. Beatriz B. Barela and Yole Palmiano

From 1982 to 1992, NEDA Region V implemented the Local Resource Management Project (LRMP) in Bicol. The project was designed to: (1) help local government respond to the needs of poor rural communities, and (2) promote a planning and development approach following the tenets of a people-centered and poverty-group focused development. Four Bicol provinces were selected as pilot sites for the project. Severity of poverty among rural population, and level of development initiatives were among the criteria for site selection.

Component and strategies

(1) Technical assistance for LGU staff in community organizing, (2) Research to enhance policy formulation, (3) Training for long-term planning of development projects, (4) Community funds management to support livelihood beneficiaries, (5) Sub-project financing for infrastructure projects, and (6) Commodities to provide logistical support to LRM efforts.

Processes adopted

Project stakeholders consisted of upland farmers, fisherfolk, landless agricultural workers and small coconut farmers; LGU officials from barangay to regional level; and regional line agencies of the government. The stakeholders participated in all stages of the project, but the LGUs played a more prominent role in site selection, the poverty study, strategy formulation, program planning, sub-project development and implementation, monitoring and evaluation, and replication.

Measures to sustain the project included creation of viable community business associations (CBOs) and private voluntary organizations (PVO), and development of loan recovery strategies for livelihood activities. Through effective community organizing, the PVOs worked towards their eventual phase-out, while the LGUs worked towards taking over the CBOs.

Results

The project contributed significantly to the design of the Local Government Code, particularly in crafting the details of operationalizing decentralization. Sustainability is one measure of success and the 1996 Audit Report of Camarines Norte reported the majority of the LRM community-managed projects succeeding during the first three years of project phase out. The same report revealed, however, low collection levels for remittances, loan repayments and collectibles.

Lessons learned

The project demonstrated that government and NGOs can collaborate rather than compete. Livelihood projects that are small, simple and linked to local resources created the strongest impact. Through the CBOs, marginal groups were able to participate in project identification, increasing thereby their access to income and resources. In the future, time required from the local communities to participate in project activities should not, however, conflict with their economic activities. While the LGUs have become more sensitive to participatory development through the project, there was still heavy reliance on external rather than local resources, owing to the slim tax base in most depressed provinces. One reflection from the project is that change in political leadership and political will have great impacts on project success or failure.

Don Tomas small water impounding project, Sta. Elena, Camarines Sur *Department of Agriculture*¹

The farmers in *barangay* Don Tomas in Sta. Elena, Camarines Norte encountered difficulties in farming due to insufficient irrigation during the dry season, and flash floods during the wet season. To mitigate the problem, the Small Water Impounding Project (SWIP) was introduced and implemented in the area from 1996 to 2001, with the aim of increasing rice production through supplemental irrigation.

Components and strategies

The construction of structures and institutional development were the two main components of the project. The former includes the construction of small water impounding structures on a 50-ha rainfed rice farm being maintained by 40 farmers. Part of the project package was the construction of farm-to-market roads. As part of institutional development, target farmers were organized and registered and given capacity development training. Relevant management policies were also formulated.

Processes adopted

Stakeholder participation from the municipal level to the *barangay* council was maximized through: (1) site validation and site survey, (2) structure design and cost analysis, and (3) periodic monitoring during small infrastructure development. Farmers and fisherfolk provided contract labor in constructing physical structures for the project.

Sustainability measures adopted included: (1) consultative meetings among stakeholders prior to project implementation, (2) organization and development of farmers/irrigators association, (3) capacity building on latest technology in rice production and integrated pest management, and (4) memo-agreement between LGU and farmers on project operations and management.

Results

Rice production of farmers using the SWIP technology increased significantly from 40 cavans/ha. to 80-100 cavans/ha. Aside from the higher farm yield, the farmers' transport expenses were reduced by a farm-to-market road.

Impounded water has also become a source of water for fishery, irrigation and livestock, thereby providing additional income for farmers. As for environmental impact, SWIP helps control flash flooding and soil erosion in farmlands. It has also contributed in improving groundwater supply.

¹ Regional Field Unit No. 5

Developing partnership for sustainable watershed management in Mount Isarog: The MNWD experience

Vicente A. Rubio

The 1990s were challenging years for the Metro Naga Water District (MNWD). The El Niño phenomenon and the degradation of forest cover in Mt. Isarog led to a decrease in the water production capacity of the water district. MNWD initiated a sustainable watershed management partnership program with the stakeholders, as a response. Overall objective was to restore, protect and conserve watershed resources and increase water availability for the district. Starting in 1992, MNWD forged partnership arrangements with communities living within the Natural Park, and with various government, NGOs, and academic institutions.

Components and strategies

(1) Community education and awareness program; (2) Nursery establishment and development; (3) Plantation establishment, maintenance, protection and conservation; (4) Micro-finance for small-scale enterprise development; (5) Backyard-vegetable production; and (6) Resettlement.

Processes adopted

Several key project strategies were identified. This include: (1) formation of an inter-agency watershed management committee involving CSSAC, DA, DOST, LWUA, DENR, Plan International, CARE-Philippines and LGUs; (2) signing of memorandum of agreement (MOA) between LWUA, the Philippine Association of Water Districts (PAWD) and the DENR; (3) stewardship agreement between the DENR and the MNWD for the rehabilitation and protection of 317ha of the Mt. Isarog watershed; and (4) a tripartite MOA between Plan International, MNWD and the Rotary Club of Naga for the development and protection of Anayan and Rumangrap springs.

Results

The formation of Mt. Isarog Guardians (MIGs), a volunteer group, effectively decreased illegal activities, especially in advocacy against treasure hunting in the park. Farmers were trained on cooperative management, bio-intensive gardening, solid waste management, environmental education, sustainable agricultural practices and alternative livelihoods.

Lessons learned

Alleviating poverty in a resettlement program can best be achieved through social transformation. The seminar-workshops were effective in promoting awareness and social responsibility among high school students on watershed management. Participation of various stakeholders and clarified roles among them helped in the convergence of assistance and in the efficient administration of resources. How to sustain the various programs remains a challenge, however, as some long-held values and mindsets such as, dole-out mentality and continuing dependence of some farmers on aid, and idleness and individualism among some community members make maintaining and sustaining community livelihood projects difficult.

Community-based resource management project: Abasig-Matagdon watershed development sub-project

Provincial CBRM Team², Camarines Norte

The Abasig-Matagdon watershed development subproject (of a CBNRM project) was implemented in Barangay Tulay na Lupa, Labo, Camarines Norte from 2000-2002. The project addresses interrelated resource management issues such as, timber poaching and collection of minor forest products; poverty issues such as, low family income, poor farm-to-market roads and malnutrition. Specifically, the subproject aimed to develop 300ha using appropriate reforestation schemes, livelihood support and community development approaches.

Components and strategies

(1) Natural resource management, including reforestation of a 200ha logged-over area of the watershed; (2) Livelihood support, e.g., crops and livestock production; (3) Small-scale infrastructures, e.g.; graded trails and look-out towers; and (4) Community organizing and capability-building on organizational and livelihood management.

Processes adopted

DENR, DA, the Camarines Sur Water District, the LGU from provincial to the *barangay* council level, selected community-based organizations (CBO), and the youth sector comprised the CBRM project stakeholders. They were involved from project planning, particularly in problem diagnosis and capacity-building and were part of multi-sectoral teams formed to monitor project activities and evaluate project impact. A *barangay* resource management team composed of, health workers and agriculturists was also formed and participated in local planning.

Sustainability mechanisms employed by the project: (1) selection of CBOs with demonstrated capability to handle development projects, (2) semestral GOP-World Bank supervision missions regularly assessed project outcomes, (3) formulation of a five-year sustainability/transition plan required the provincial government to provide 20% development fund for the protection of the project area, and (4) concerned sectors continuously manage the small-scale infrastructure.

Results

The project contributed to uplifting the economic condition of farmers, developed self-reliant communities and enhanced the biological niche for biodiversity. At the end of the project life: (1) 200ha of degraded portions of watershed had been reforested, and other portions were developed into agroforestry farms; (2) livelihood support and training packages were provided to close to a hundred households; (3) various training courses were provided to local organizations.

Lessons learned

Partnership between LGU and NGOs were helpful in the community organizing aspect. Participatory approaches identify and successfully implement the livelihood options and develop a livelihood management plan. Community awareness is best facilitated through effective information, education and communication. Absence of concrete guidelines, particularly on fund management delayed project implementation. WB and CBRMP policies and guidelines for project approval were often difficult to comply with, hampering project operations. But involvement of different sectors in project review helped to improve project planning to attain project objectives.

² Staff from the Provincial Planning and Development Office, the Office of the Provincial Agriculturist, Office of the Provincial Veterinarian, Provincial Engineer's Office, Office of the Governor-Ecosystem and Environmental Resource Management Division and DENR, Province of Camarines Norte.

Best practices in Naga City river strategic watershed management program

Oscar P. Orozco

The Naga River is a vital part of Naga City's ecosystem and economy. Years of abuse had turned the river murky with silt and garbage, that it could no longer effectively serve commerce and human needs. In 1996, the people and officials of Naga City realizing the serious situation, took steps to develop a 10-year strategic management plan for the Naga watershed.

Components and strategies

Identified were the following priority activities and action points for implementation: (1) reforestation of the upland areas of the watershed; (2) implementation of the Naga City revetment, dredging and beautification project; (3) improvement of solid waste management; and (4) strengthening of sectoral, *barangay* and people's council's participation. The city government provided the necessary budget.

Strategies to rehabilitate and manage the river include: (1) river park development, physical rehabilitation of river and waterways, and watershed vegetative cover restoration; (2) education and sustained pollution prevention by households and institutions; (3) regulatory policy strategies on watershed management; and (4) institutional development.

Processes adopted

Representatives from the city government, national line agencies, NGOs and Naga City residents participated in a multi-sectoral workshop to identify key action points for a management plan. This was followed by seminar-workshop consultations and site analysis to evolve the management plan. The final output was presented to local executives and the City Council.

To ensure the plan's sustained implementation, these measures were undertaken: (1) a separate Environment and Natural Resources Office (ENRO) in the city government office was established, (2) funds for plan implementation were allocated, (3) very specific doable activities in the plan were identified, and (4) support policies drafted. The city ENRO was tasked with the primary management role supported by the multi-sectoral Environment Management Council (EMC). Activities in the plan have been incorporated into the city budget. Supplemental funds for river revetment were sourced from DPWH, while reforestation activities were supported by DENR.

Results

The project transformed the riverbank's easement strips into recreational parks, strengthened the riverbank's retaining wall, enhanced partnership with stakeholders for protection of the surrounding forests, reforested the surrounding watershed areas. It established network with various groups for watershed rehabilitation, and launched mass awareness campaigns using social marketing approaches to generate support for river beautification and rehabilitation.

Lessons learned

Formulating a river and watershed management plan requires a careful and thorough participatory process and should involve critical stakeholders at the local level. The combined efforts of stakeholders and technical consultants helped to accomplish a comprehensive plan. The support of NGOs, GOs and people's organizations was crucial in all stages of the project. Clearly identifying and ordering priorities of doable activities in the management plan helped facilitate implementation, fund allocation, and resource generation for the project.

Libon resource management project: Community-based resource management

John V. Dycoco, Leonardo M. Olivares, Salve M. Nidea and Jeffrey R. Sapillar

The Community-based Resource Management Project (CRMP) is a four-year project implemented in seven *barangays* in Libon, Albay from 2001-2004. The project was conceptualized to address the interrelated problems of forest degradation, coral reef destruction, marginal productivity of the agricultural lands, and low fish catch. Specifically, the project aimed to: (1) enhance the knowledge and build the capacity of stakeholders in natural resource and livelihood management; (2) rehabilitate, protect and manage forest and marine resources; and (3) enhance farm and fish production to provide other livelihood options.

Components and strategies

(1) Upland resource management through sloping agroforestry land technology and the provision of tenurial rights to upland farmers, (2) Coastal resource management to protect mangrove and coral reefs, (3) Livelihood development for POs and other stakeholders formerly engaged in destructive forest and fishing activities to have alternative sources of income, and (4) Community development through knowledge build-up and capacity building using various methods.

Processes adopted

Forest occupants, upland farmers, *barangay* development councils and concerned government organizations such as DENR and the LGU were among the stakeholders involved in all stages of the project, from conceptualization to implementation. Activities included resource assessment, problem and issues identification, priority setting, work and financial planning, and project proposals preparation for funding by the Department of Finance.

Sustainability measures adopted: (1) stakeholders' involvement in participatory rural appraisal, (2) community organizing and capacity-building of POs and LGUs for livelihood management, (3) setting up of policies, e.g. forced savings on contracted work to sustain the livelihood activities after project, and (4) awarding of tenurial instruments to qualified POs.

Results

As the project is midway into implementation, it is too early to measure impacts. Some early projects outputs: completion of the organizational and capacity building activities, deputation of fish wardens for forest protection, formulation of policies to sustain the livelihood operations and management, and enhanced partnership with the LGU.

Lessons learned

Commitment of project staff, cooperation of the POs and positive support from the local chief executive contributed immensely to project success. Some hindering factors, however, include social and capital issues such as, conflict of interests among PO members, internal politics, and frequent turnover of community organizer. Highly technical policies and procedures in fund reimbursements were difficult for the POs to comprehend, thus causing delays in fund releases. Provision of tenurial instrument to qualified POs has inculcated in them a sense of ownership and custody over their natural resources. Private lands located in watershed areas have been a constant source of tension and conflict, particularly in forest protection and management.

Annex 2

Directory of workshop participants and organizers

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Annex 3
Workshop schedule

**Workshop on Integrated Watershed Resources Management
Approaches for Poverty Alleviation in the Bicol Region, Philippines:
Learning from Past Experiences**

*Camarines Sur State Agricultural College (CSSAC)
Pili, Camarines Sur, Bicol
28-30 May 2003*

Wed, 28 May		
8:30 - 10:00	Registration	Lilibeth T. Sulit
10:00 - 10:15	Break	
10:15 - 2:00	Opening session	Opening Prayer (<i>Albert Adison</i>) National Anthem (<i>Tess Lirag</i>) Welcome Remarks (<i>Dr. Wilfredo G. Olaño</i>) Opening Remarks (<i>Eduardo A. Sabio</i>) Introduction of Participants Intermission (<i>Joy Cirujales</i>) Workshop Overview (<i>Kennedy N. Igbokwe</i>) <i>Master Ceremonies (Mary Ann Leones)</i>
12:00 - 1:00	Break	
1:00 - 5:00	Workshop 1 Review of case studies by cluster groups (upland, coastal and watershed ecosystems)	Group Facilitators: Jerry Bigornia Art Estrella Ed Sabio
7:00	Dinner and Socials	
Thurs, 29 May		
8:30-12:00	Workshop 2 Inter-Cluster group sharing and plenary presentation/ Analysis of case studies across cluster	Group Facilitators Nilma Garchitorena Art Estrella Yolanda Castroverde Choy Cadag
12:00 - 1:00	Lunch Break	

Date/ Time	Session/ Activities	Presentations/ Discussions
1:00 - 5:00	<p>Workshop 3 Analysis to jointly derive key elements of "holistic" watershed management</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Technical inputs on holistic watershed management 2. IIRR learning community program in Bicol 3. Issues and implications of case studies, and readiness for holistic watershed management 	<p>Kennedy N. Igbokwe</p> <p>Eduardo A. Sabio</p> <p><i>Group Facilitators:</i> Ruby L. Mendones Jeffrey Sapillar Choy Cadag</p>
<p>Fri, 30 May</p> <p>8:30-12:00</p>	<p>Plenary Workshop</p> <p>Framework for holistic watershed management</p>	<p>Eduardo A. Sabio Tabrez Nazar Kennedy N. Igbokwe</p>
12:00 - 1:00	Lunch Break	
1:00 - 3:00	What's Next?	Eduardo A. Sabio
3:00	Closing Session	<p>Workshop Evaluation (Mary Ann Leones/ Sammy Operio)</p> <p>Workshop Impressions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - LGU Participants - PO/ NGO Participants <p>Awarding of Certificates (Eduardo Sabio & Dr. Wilfredo Olaño)</p> <p>Closing Remarks (Marlene Ca. Rodriguez)</p> <p>Closing Prayer (Albert Adison)</p>

In partnership with:

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